

Inclinations in Enrolment of Students in School Education in India After Independence

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Abstract

Economic development of any country is determined by the enrolment of the children to the schools, Colleges and Universities in the modern days. Less education level leads to lesser level of economic development. Stimulation of the economic development is directly determined by the level of enrolment of the children to all levels of education in education sector. There are greater changes in the enrolment to educational institutions Indian education sector. The present paper assesses the changing trends in the enrolment from 1950 to 2016.

Keywords: Economic Development, Enrolment, Education Sector.

Introduction

This paper has made an attempt to examine the level of enrolment to the Primary, Upper Primary and Secondary Schools in India from 1950 to 2016. The data has collected from the Educational Statistics of the MHRD of Government of India. These three types of school levels have been taken to examine the enrolment and the detailed analysis has been made with the help of the suitable tables, graphs and statistical tools such as trend line values.

Graph 1 Enrolment of All Categories of Students in Primary (I-V) School education in India

From the graph-1 it can be examined that the male enrolment was high as compared to the female enrolment in India during the period from 1950 to 2016 in the Primary School level. The total enrolment to the Primary Schools in India had been increased gradually every year at the rate of 65.63 lakhs students.

Table 1: Enrolment of All Categories of Students in School education in India

Level/ Year	Primary (I-V)			Upper Primary (VI-VIII)			Secondary (IX-X)		
	Male	Female	Total	Male	Female	Total	Male	Female	Total
1950-51	138	54	192	26	5	31	NA	NA	NA
1960-61	236	114	350	51	16	67	NA	NA	NA
1970-71	357	213	570	94	39	133	NA	NA	NA
1980-81	453	285	738	139	68	207	NA	NA	NA
2000-01	640	498	1138	253	175	428	116	74	190
2005-06	705	616	1321	289	233	522	145	105	250
2006-07	711	626	1337	299	246	545	149	110	259
2007-08	711	644	1355	311	262	573	159	123	282
2008-09	706	647	1353	314	270	584	165	130	295
2009-10	697	639	1336	317	278	595	169	138	307
2010-11	701	646	1347	327	292	619	175	143	318
2011-12	726	672	1398	331	299	630	186	155	341
2012-13	696	652	1348	333	317	650	183	163	346
2013-14	686	638	1324	341	323	664	197	176	373
2014-15	676	629	1305	345	327	672	201	182	383
2015-16	669	622	1291	347	329	676	205	186	391

Graph 2 Enrolment of All Categories of Students in Upper Primary (VI-VIII) School Education in India

The enrolment to the Upper Primary schools in India is also gradually improving and it is noted that here also the male enrolment has taking lead as compared to the female enrolment during the study period of time as shown in the graph-2. The enrolment to the Upper Primary has been increased at the magnitude of 43.276 lakhs students every year and attained the positive increase in the enrolment.

Graph 3 Enrolment of All Categories of Students in Secondary (IX-X) School education in India

The enrolment to the Secondary school level also had been increased at the amount of 16.346 lakhs student over the period of time in India in each year. It has achieved a positive growth in the enrolment to this secondary level of education across the country. The graph-3 also shows that the male enrolment was increased as compared to the female enrolment to the Secondary schools in India. Here also female enrolment is lagging behind.

Conclusion

The study found that the female enrolment to the primary, upper primary and secondary school level in India had been lagging behind as compared to the male enrolment. It means female enrolment need to be increased in India through the policy implementations. Overall the enrolment to all three types of school levels had been increased gradually from 1950 to 2016 it is a positive indicator in the school education system in India.

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